

1 **Characterization of monilia disease caused by *Monilinia linhartiana* on quince in**
2 **southern Spain**

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14 **ABSTRACT**

15
16 This study elucidated the aetiology and epidemiology of monilia disease of quince
17 caused by the fungus *Monilinia linhartiana* in Spain. Disease incidence and the
18 dynamics of apothecial development and ascospore discharge were quantified and the
19 pathogen was characterized morphologically and molecularly. The pathogen did not
20 produce conidia or apothecia on agar media but produced conidia on symptomatic
21 leaves and apothecia on mummified young quince fruit. *M. linhartiana* was not
22 pathogenic to ripe quince fruit but was readily isolated from developing, mummified
23 fruit (pseudosclerotia). Phylogenetic analysis based on 5.8S-ITS region sequences
24 placed *M. linhartiana* in the *Disjuntoriae* section of *Monilinia* species infecting
25 rosaceous hosts. Studies during 2004-2008 in four commercial orchards in southern
26 Spain determined two major infection periods of the disease. The first infection period
27 coincided with the unfolding of the first leaves and resulted in leaf blotch and shoot

1 blight. The second coincided with flowering and led to mummification of developing
2 young fruit. Apparently, foliar infection was initiated by airborne ascospores produced
3 on pseudosclerotia that overwintered on the soil surface, while flower infection was
4 probably initiated by conidia produced on leaf lesions. Incidence of diseased shoots
5 ranged from 1 to 91% and was correlated with calculated inoculum potential, which was
6 based on the density and maturity of apothecia formed on pseudosclerotia. This
7 epidemiological study has made it possible to characterise the life cycle of monilia
8 disease on quince in southern Spain, which will help the development of new control
9 strategies.

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11 *Keywords:* disease forecasting, epidemiology, *Monilinia linhartiana*, phylogeny,
12 taxonomy.

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15 **Introduction**

16 Quince (*Cydonia oblonga*) is a traditional crop in Spain where the annual production is
17 20,000 metric tons; production is concentrated in the Subbética zone of the Andalucía
18 region in southern Spain. Quince has been cultivated in Andalucía since the 1st century
19 AD (Columela, Century I) but its agronomic features have seldom been studied in this
20 region. Quince has an enormous cultural importance in the Subbética zone, where it is
21 an important component of the diet and grows close to olive orchards (Cabello, 2008).

22 The most important disease of quince in southern Spain and one of the most
23 destructive diseases of quince worldwide, is monilia disease caused by the fungus
24 *Monilinia linhartiana* (anamorph: *Monilia cydoniae*) (Batra, 1991). This pathogen often

1 destroys the entire quince crop (Viennot-Bourgin, 1949; Moral *et al.*, 2008). However,
2 there are no estimates of the incidence of this disease in southern Spain because
3 monilia disease is often confused with other diseases or disorders, such as frost damage,
4 physiological fruit drop or black rot caused by *Botryosphaeria obtusa* (Moral *et al.*,
5 2007; Cabello, 2008).

6 Species in the genus *Monilinia* have been divided into two sections:
7 *Disjunctoriae* and *Junctoriae*. These sections were defined on the basis of conidial
8 morphology, fungus life cycle and host specialization, and have been accepted by most
9 researchers (Batra, 1991; Holst-Jensen *et al.*, 1997). The difference between the
10 *Disjunctoriae* and *Junctoriae* sections has been confirmed by studies of internal
11 transcribed spacers (ITS1 and ITS2) and the 5.8 subunit of the nuclear ribosomal DNA
12 (Holst-Jensen *et al.*, 1997; Harada *et al.*, 2005; Takahashi *et al.*, 2005). *M. linhartiana* is
13 in the *Disjunctoriae* section but there have been few studies on its identification and
14 biology (Batra, 1991). A sequence of the ITS1-5.8S-ITS2 region of *M. linhartiana*
15 would increase our understanding of its relationship to other *Monilinia* species and the
16 phylogenetic of the genus *Monilinia* (Holst-Jensen *et al.*, 1997).

17 The life cycle of *M. linhartiana* on quince trees may be similar to that of *M.*
18 *vaccinii-corymbosi* on blueberry, with two separate cycles of infection: foliar infection
19 initiated by ascospores produced on mummified fruit (pseudosclerotia) that overwinter
20 on the soil surface and flower infection initiated by conidia produced on the diseased
21 leaves (Batra, 1991). The life cycle of pathogen on quince, however, is not well
22 understood (Viennot-Bourgin, 1949) and has never been studied in Spain.

23 Disease management requires information about inoculum dynamics and the
24 timing of symptom development; such information helps orchard managers to time

1 fungicide treatments and cultural practices (Campbell & Madden, 1990; Michailides *et*
2 *al.*, 2007). The dynamics of apothecial development and ascospore production by *M.*
3 *linhartiana* in relation to infection are unknown. As is the case with management of
4 other pathogens that cause monocyclic diseases or epidemics with few secondary
5 cycles, the management of *M. linhartiana* is based on control of primary infections
6 caused by ascospores (Campbell & Madden, 1990).

7 The overall objective of this study was to increase our understanding of the
8 aetiology and epidemiology of monilia disease of quince. The specific objectives were
9 (i) to characterize the pathogen (morphologically and molecularly), (ii) to quantify
10 pathogen development (apothecial development and ascospore discharge) and (iii) to
11 quantify disease incidence in crops. The critical time for control of *M. linhartiana* on
12 quince (in terms of host phenology) was also determined. A preliminary report of this
13 study has been published (Moral *et al.*, 2008).

14 **Materials and methods**

15 **Disease incidence**

16 The occurrence of monilia disease in the Subbética region of southern Spain was
17 evaluated in quince orchards from 2004 to 2008. In the first year (2004), disease was
18 assessed in 10 orchards distributed across all the main areas where quince is cultivated
19 in. No fungicide sprays were applied in any of these orchards. From 2005 to 2008,
20 disease occurrence was assessed in four orchards that were selected from the original 10
21 as representative of the region, El Algar, La Mendaña, El Palancar and Zagrilla Baja. In
22 May of each year, 10 trees (replications) of cv. Común in each field were selected and
23 250 to 500 shoots per tree were assessed for disease incidence, which was calculated as
24 the percentage of shoots showing typical disease symptoms (leaf blotch, shoot blight, or

1 mummification of developing fruit). In 2004, the data for percentages of shoots affected
2 by *M. linhartiana* were analyzed by a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) to
3 determine whether disease incidence differed among the 10 orchards. For the four
4 selected orchards that were assessed from 2004 to 2008, a combined ANOVA was used
5 to determine whether disease incidence was affected by orchard, year or the interaction
6 between orchard and year (Gomez & Gomez, 1984). Before analyses, percentage data
7 were converted into proportions that were then arcsine transformed to homogenize the
8 variances. When ANOVAs indicated that differences between orchard or year were
9 significant, transformed mean values were compared by the Fisher's Protected Least
10 Significant Difference (LSD) test at $P = 0.05$. Data from all experiments were analyzed
11 using Statistix 9 (Analytical Software, Tallahassee, Florida).

12 **Morphology of *M. linhartiana***

13 In 2005 and 2006, 12 isolates of *M. linhartiana* were collected from naturally infected
14 leaves on quince trees in two orchards (Zagrilla Baja and El Palancar) (Table 1).
15 Conidia from infected leaves were placed in 9-cm-diameter Petri dishes containing
16 potato dextrose agar (PDA; Difco Laboratories) acidified with 2.5 ml of a 25% lactic
17 acid solution per litre of medium. Petri dishes were incubated at $23 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ with a 12-h
18 photoperiod of fluorescent light ($350 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$) for 1 week. Pure cultures of *M.*
19 *linhartiana* were obtained by transferring hyphal tips from the margins of colonies
20 growing on acidified PDA to other Petri dishes. The cultures were maintained in the
21 fungal collection of the Department of Agronomy at the University of Córdoba,
22 Córdoba, Spain. Three of the isolates (MON-06, MON-07 and MON-08) were also
23 cultured on PDA where they developed microconidia after 15 days. Length, width,
24 shape and colour of 50 conidia per isolate were determined using a compound
25 microscope (Nikon Eclipse 80i, Nikon Corp.) and Nis-Element D software (Nikon

1 Instruments, Inc.). Two isolates of *M. laxa* and three of *M. fructigena* (Table 1) were
2 obtained from A. de Cal of the National Institute for Agricultural Research (INIA,
3 Madrid) and were used for comparison with *M. linhartiana*.

4 Apothecia of *M. linhartiana* were obtained from mummified quince fruit
5 (pseudosclerotia) that had overwintered on the soil surface. In total sixty
6 pseudosclerotia with apothecia were collected from two orchards (Zagrilla Baja and El
7 Palancar) and placed in plastic moisture chambers ($22 \times 16 \times 10 \text{ cm}^3$) at 10°C with
8 100% relative humidity (RH). In the laboratory, the apothecia were classified using a 1
9 to 5 scale (Cabello, 2008), where 1 = apothecium cup not formed; 2 = initial formation
10 of the cup; 3 = cup concave with the edge enlarged; 4 = cup completely developed with
11 a smooth edge; and 5 = senescing apothecium with few or no ascospores. In this
12 classification, stages 3 and 4 indicate apothecia with mature ascospores. Forty apothecia
13 in stages 3 and 4 were dissected from the pseudosclerotia, and the diameter of the
14 apothecial cup and the width and length of the apothecial stipe were measured. Length
15 and width of 60 asci and 600 ascospores from 20 pseudosclerotia were measured.

16 **Characteristics of *M. linhartiana* on agar culture**

17 Production of conidia in culture media and other characteristics of growth in culture
18 were evaluated by growing isolates of *M. laxa* (MON-01 and MON-02), *M. fructigena*
19 (MON-04 and MON-05), and *M. linhartiana* (MON-06 and MON-07) on seven media.
20 Five of the media were prepared according to Dhingra & Sinclair (1985); PDA, saline
21 PDA, oat meal agar (OMA), V-8 juice agar (V8) and peach agar (PA). The other two
22 media were PDA plus acetone (Pascual *et al.*, 1990) and V-8 juice agar with a cellulose
23 membrane (Brewster *et al.*, 1995). A 5-mm-diameter plug from the growing margin of
24 a 5-day-old colony was placed in the centre of a 9-cm-diameter Petri dish containing

1 one of the seven media. The Petri dishes were incubated at $23 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ with a 12-h
2 photoperiod. Colony diameter was measured after 7 and 14 days, and data were
3 converted to radial growth (mm per day). After 14 days, the shape of the colony and the
4 presence of zonation, microconidia and conidia were determined. Three replicate Petri
5 dishes were used for each combination of isolate and medium. The test was done twice
6 and the similar data from the two experiments were ($P = 0.465$) were averaged.
7 ANOVA was used to determine whether radial growth was affected by treatment
8 variables isolate, medium, or the interaction between isolate and medium. Mean values
9 were compared using the Fisher's Protected LSD test at $P = 0.05$.

10 **Molecular characterization of *M. linhartiana***

11 Fungal mycelium for DNA extraction was obtained from four isolates of *M. linhartiana*
12 (from MON-07 to MON-10) grown on PDA for 10 days. Mycelium was collected from
13 the surface of the PDA. Genomic DNA was extracted using the FastDNA Kit (BIO 101,
14 Inc.) following the manufacturer's instructions. The nuclear ribosomal DNA repeat
15 including ITS1, 5.8S rRNA, and ITS2 and portions of the genes encoding both small
16 and large subunit rRNAs were amplified using primers ITS1 and ITS4 according to
17 White *et al.* (1990). The PCR products were purified using an Ultra Clean PCR Clean-
18 Up Kit (Mobio Laboratories, Inc.). The resulting amplicons were sequenced in both
19 directions using an automated sequencer (ABI Prism 3130XL; Applied Biosystems) by
20 the Central Sequencing Service of the University of Córdoba in Spain. The nucleotide
21 sequences were read and edited with FinchTV 1.4.0 (Geospiza Inc.; <http://www.geospiza.com/flinchtv>). All sequences were checked manually and nucleotide
22 arrangements at ambiguous positions were clarified using direction sequences of both
23 primers. Additionally, sequences of the strains isolated in this study were compared
24 with those *Monilinia* sequences available in GenBank: *M. amelanchieris* (Z73769), *M.*
25

1 *aucupariae* (Z73771), *M. azaleae* (AB182266), *M. baccarum* (Z73773), *M. cassiopes*
2 (Z73776), *M. fruticola* (Z73777), *M. fructigena* (Z73781), *M. gaylussaciae* (Z73782),
3 *M. jezoensis* (AB182265), *M. johnsonii* (Z73783), *M. laxa* (Z73786), *M. mali*
4 (AB125615), *Monilia megalospora* (Z73788), *M. mumecola* (AB125618), *M. oxycocci*
5 (Z73789), *M. padi* (Z73791), *M. polycodii* (Z73782), *M. polystroma* (Y17876), *M.*
6 *seaverii* (Z73793), *M. urnula* (Z73794), *M. vaccinii-corymbosi* (Z73796), *Ovulinia*
7 *azaleae* (Z73797) and *Sclerotinia sclerotiorum* (Z73783) (Holst-Jensen *et al.*, 1997;
8 Harada *et al.*, 2005; Takahashi *et al.*, 2005). The 5.8S-ITS region sequences were
9 aligned using the computer program MEGA version 4.0 (Tamura *et al.*, 2007). To
10 obtain appropriate substitution models for Maximum Likelihood (ML) analysis
11 (Felsenstein, 1981), the alignment was analysed with jModelTest 0.1.1 using the Akaike
12 information criterion (AIC) (Posada, 2008). Searches for the best ML tree and 1000
13 bootstrap replications were done with the fast likelihood software PHYML 3.0, using
14 identical settings.

15 **Pathogenicity tests on ripe fruit and infection of developing fruit**

16 Completely gold-yellow ripe fruit of cv. Común collected during autumn were
17 inoculated with two isolates of *M. linhartiana* (MON-08 and MON-09), two isolates of
18 *M. laxa* (MON-01 and MON-02) or two isolates of *M. fructigena* (MON-04 and MON-
19 05) (Table 1). Before inoculation, the fruit were washed and then surface sterilized by
20 immersing them in a 10% solution of commercial NaClO (50 g Cl per litre). Surface
21 sterilized fruit were inoculated by placing on them a 9-mm-diameter PDA plug of
22 mycelium of each isolate. Control fruit were treated with a sterile PDA plug. Control
23 and inoculated fruit were placed in plastic moisture chambers (41 × 26 × 20 cm) at
24 100% RH and 22 ± 2°C under fluorescent lights (350 µmol m⁻²·s⁻¹). There were five

1 fruit per isolate and the experiment was repeated three times. Fruit were weekly
2 examined for disease symptoms and lesions that formed around the agar plugs were
3 measured after 1 month. The effects of species and isolate on lesion diameter were
4 determined by an ANOVA and means were compared by the Fisher's Protected LSD
5 test at $P = 0.05$.

6 To study whether the fungus infects the developing fruit, a total of 10 aborted
7 fruit (< 10 mm diameter) with initial symptoms of mummification were collected from
8 each of two quince orchards during the spring. Mummies were washed, surface
9 sterilized and air dried on a laboratory bench. Small pieces ($3 \times 3 \times 3$ mm) of
10 mummified fruit (5 pieces per fruit) were placed on acidified PDA in Petri dishes. The
11 Petri dishes were incubated at $23 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ with a 12-h photoperiod. The percentage of fruit
12 pieces with *M. linhartiana* was assessed 7 days after the pieces had been placed on
13 PDA. The experiment was repeated three times, i.e. 300 pieces of fruit from 60
14 mummified fruit were examined.

15 **Effect of temperature on mycelial growth and apothecial development**

16 Petri dishes containing potato sucrose agar (PSA; Harada *et al.*, 2005) were inoculated
17 with 5-mm-diameter mycelial plugs (one plug per plate) taken from the edge of actively
18 growing 10-day-old cultures of *M. linhartiana*. The dishes were independently
19 incubated in the dark at 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30 and 35°C . Colony diameter was measured
20 daily. There were five replicate dishes per isolate (MON-08 and MON-09) and
21 temperature, and the experiment was done twice. The results of the two trials were
22 similar, and thus the data were averaged across trials. For each isolate, regressions of
23 radial growth (mm per day) against temperature were done. The Student's *t*-test was

1 used to compare optimal temperatures (°C) for radial growth, maximum daily radial
2 growth (mm) and area under the growth curve of the isolate.

3 The effect of temperature on apothecial development was also determined using
4 48 pseudosclerotia with apothecial initials (phenological stage 1 and 2 of the maturity
5 scale) that were collected from the Zagrilla Baja quince orchard. The mummified fruit
6 were divided into four replicate groups (12 fruit per group) so that the groups did not
7 differ in numbers and maturity of apothecia. Each group was placed in a separate plastic
8 moisture chamber (22 × 16 × 10 cm, 100% RH) at 6, 12, 18 or 24°C under fluorescent
9 lights (350 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$). The phenological stage of each apothecium was assessed daily
10 on a 1 to 5 scale. The experiment was done twice with similar results and the data were
11 combined for analysis. The relationship between incubation temperature and apothecial
12 development rate was evaluated by linear regression using an equation forced through
13 the origin. In all linear regression analyses, the following were determined: the
14 significance of the regression, the coefficient of determination (R^2), the coefficient of
15 determination adjusted for degrees of freedom (R_a^2) and the pattern of residuals. The
16 slopes of the four regression lines generated by different incubation temperatures were
17 compared after doing the Bartlett test for equality of variance by using the least
18 significant difference test at $P = 0.05$.

19 **Apothecial development and ascospore dynamics in orchards**

20 Apothecial development and ascospore dynamics were quantified in two quince
21 orchards (El Palancar and Zagrilla Baja) from budbreak to fruit set (February to April)
22 of 2006 and 2007 and in one quince orchard (El Palancar) in the same period of 2008.
23 Five trees were selected in each orchard, and 4 m² of soil surrounding each tree were
24 examined every 7-10 days. The following variables were quantified: the number of

1 mummified fruit with at least one apothecium, the number of apothecia per mummified
2 fruit, the phenological stage of the apothecia (1–4; apothecia at stage 5 were not counted
3 because they release few or no ascospores), the number of mummified fruit and the
4 number of apothecia per m². Inoculum potential (IP) for each tree was calculated as:

5

$$IP = \frac{\sum n_i \times e_i}{S}$$

6

7 where n_i = number of apothecia, e_i = phenological stage (< 5) of each apothecium and
8 S = sampled area (4 m²).

9 Airborne ascospores of *M. linhartiana* were quantified with a spore sampler
10 (Burkard Manufacturing Co. Ltd.) that was placed 1.5 m above ground level in one
11 quince orchard (El Palancar) for 2 years (2006 and 2007). The trap was operated from
12 February to April and the sticky tape that collected the spores was replaced weekly.
13 Once removed from the field, the tape was cut into daily segments (48 mm), which were
14 examined every other day. The entire area of each daily segment was scanned with a
15 microscope (×200 magnification) and the number of *M. linhartiana* ascospores per hour
16 (per 2 mm of tape) was counted.

17 **Relationships between inoculum, disease and weather variables**

18 Pearson correlation and linear regression analyses were used to evaluate the
19 relationships between average and maximum values of inoculum variables (mummified
20 fruit / m², apothecia / mummified fruit, apothecia / m², inoculum potential) and the
21 percentage of diseased shoots in two orchards (El Palancar and Zagrilla Baja).

1 Multiple linear regression analysis was used to characterize relationships between daily
2 concentration of airborne ascospores and the daily average of different weather
3 variables (rainfall, temperature, relative humidity and wind speed) for one orchard in
4 two years. Weather variables were measured at a weather station located 12 km from
5 the experimental orchard. Influence of weather on days $x - n$ ($n = 1$ to 7) on ascospore
6 concentration on day x was also studied. The best model was selected using a stepwise
7 linear regression method (Statistix 9). Thus, the hourly distribution of ascospore counts
8 from the sampling period was studied. The cumulative number of ascospores collected
9 over time was fitted using the logistic model $[Ln(Y_i)/(Y_{max}-Y_i)]$, where Y_i is the number
10 of ascospores collected per day and Y_{max} is maximum number of ascospores collected in
11 one day. Logit-transformed ascospores data were regressed against days (Campbell and
12 Madden, 1990). Finally, Pearson's correlation test and linear regression were used to
13 assess relationships between the mean disease incidence (%) in each year and the
14 rainfall during the first 25 days of March.

15 **Results**

16 **Disease incidence**

17 All quince trees examined during the study (2004 to 2008) had symptoms of monilia
18 disease. The pathogen caused two types of symptom in orchards, leaf blotch and shoot
19 blight (Figs. 1a and 1b) and mummification of developing young fruit (Figs. 1c and 1d).
20 The diseased leaves infected by *M. linhartiana* smelt aromatic, mimicking the smell of
21 quince flowers. Incidence of diseased shoots ranged from 0.9% (in the Zagrilla Baja
22 orchard in 2008) to 91.5% (in the El Palancar orchard in 2006) (Fig. 2). Sampling year,
23 orchard, and the interaction between year and orchard significantly influenced ($P <$
24 0.001 in all cases) the percentage of shoots infected by the pathogen. Because the

1 interaction between year and orchard was significant, orchards were compared within
2 each year. Disease incidence across the orchards was greatest in 2006, when 75% of the
3 shoots showed symptoms, whereas the average disease incidence was only about 6% in
4 2005 and 2008 (Fig. 2).

5 **Morphology of *M. linhartiana***

6 The pathogen produced chains of up to 30 conidia with disjunctors on diseased leaves
7 during the spring. Conidia were limoniform and hyaline and had smooth walls. There
8 were small differences in the size of conidia between isolates (*data not shown*), which
9 ranged from $6.4\text{--}17.2 \times 5.1\text{--}13.6 \mu\text{m}$. The mean \pm SD conidium length and width were
10 $10.5 \pm 1.7 \times 8.5 \pm 1.1 \mu\text{m}$. On PDA, the pathogen developed microconidia, which were
11 subglobose to pyriform and hyaline and measured $3.5 \pm 0.4 \times 3.2 \pm 1.1 \mu\text{m}$. *M.*
12 *linhartiana* developed solitary or multiple apothecia (2-12) on mummified fruit that had
13 overwintered on the soil surface or were slightly buried in the soil. Mature apothecia
14 were brown to pale brown and cupulate or planoconvex. Apothecia at phenological
15 stage 3 (cup concave with the edge enlarged) had a stipe that was $30.7 \pm 15.7 \text{ mm}$ long
16 $\times 0.8 \pm 1.1 \text{ mm}$ wide and a cup diameter of $20.7 \pm 5.8 \text{ mm}$. Apothecial stage 4 (cup
17 completely developed with a smooth edge) had a stipe that was $56.1 \pm 34.9 \times 0.7 \pm 0.3$
18 mm and cup diameter of $30.6 \pm 9.4 \text{ mm}$. Asci of *M. linhartiana* were cylindrical to
19 claviform and measured $98.6 \pm 24.7 \times 7.2 \pm 1.9 \mu\text{m}$. Ascospores were ellipsoid, hyaline
20 and smooth-walled. Ascospores measured $10.1 \pm 1.0 \times 5.6 \pm 1.1 \mu\text{m}$. Paraphyses were
21 cylindrical to claviform and slightly longer ($1\text{--}2 \mu\text{m}$) than asci.

22 **Characteristics of *M. linhartiana* in agar culture**

23 Isolates of *Monilinia* species grew on all culture media. The species, medium, and
24 interaction between species and medium significantly ($P < 0.001$) affected mycelial

1 growth (*data not shown*). In general, *M. linhartiana* grew better in media with potato
2 extracts than in other media. Colonies of *M. linhartiana* were white, almost grey in the
3 centre, fluffy and had complete margins after 10 days on PDA at $23 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. *M.*
4 *fructigena* colonies were brownish grey and felt-like, with dense mycelium and
5 complete margins on PDA. In contrast, *M. laxa* colonies were yellowish grey and felt-
6 like, with lobed margins. Production of conidia and microconidia differed greatly
7 between *Monilinia* species. *M. fructigena* formed conidia on all media except PDA but
8 *M. laxa* and *M. linhartiana* did not form conidia on any media. *M. linhartiana*
9 developed microconidia on all media but *M. fructigena* and *M. laxa* did not form
10 microconidia.

11 **Molecular characterization of *M. linhartiana***

12 The 5.8S-ITS region of *M. linhartiana* contained 480 bp. The alignment of the ITS
13 sequences showed that the ITS1 was more variable than the ITS2, i.e. ITS1 had 42 sites
14 while ITS2 had 38 nucleotide sites that varied among the isolates studied. The AIC
15 criterion as implemented in jModelTest suggested GTR+G as the most appropriate
16 substitution model. The log likelihood of the best ML tree found was -1,862. The 25
17 representative isolates of *Monilinia* spp. formed three major groups (I, II and III)
18 supported by bootstrap values $> 65\%$ (Fig. 3). Group I (bootstrap value 81%) included
19 all of the *Monilinia* species that belong to the *Junctoriae* section and that infect
20 rosaceous hosts; *M. johnsonii*, *Ovulinia azaleae* and *S. sclerotiorum* were also in group
21 I. Group II (bootstrap value 67%) included those *Monilinia* species that belong to the
22 *Disjunctoriae* section and that infect ericaceous and rosaceous hosts. Group III
23 (bootstrap value 100%) included only those *Monilinia* species that belong to the
24 *Disjunctoriae* section and that infect the *Ericaceae*. *M. linhartiana* belongs to group II
25 and exhibits similar sequences to and is clustered close to the reference sequence of *M.*

1 *amelanchieris*. The 5.8S-ITS sequences of *M. linhartiana* and *M. amelanchieris*
2 differed in only one nucleotide. The sequence of isolate MON-09 contained one
3 nucleotide (thymine) more at position 122 than the rest of the *M. linhartiana* isolates
4 studied. Sequences of the ITS region from two representative *M. linhartiana* isolates
5 (MON-09 and MON-10) were deposited in the GenBank (Accessions HM581953 and
6 HM581954, respectively).

7 **Pathogenicity tests on ripe fruit and infection of developing fruit**

8 The species *M. linhartiana* was not pathogenic on ripe fruit. Isolates of *M. laxa* and *M.*
9 *fructigena* were pathogenic to ripe fruit of quince cv. Común. The first symptoms (soft
10 rot) were observed 12 days after fruit were inoculated. Uninoculated fruit did not
11 develop any disease symptoms. Both species developed abundant conidia on the fruit
12 surface. *M. laxa* and *M. fructigena* did not differ in disease severity, i.e. lesion
13 diameters on inoculated fruit were similar ($P = 0.456$) for both species.

14 In quince trees infected with *M. linhartiana*, first symptoms on developing fruit
15 appeared soon after fruit set. Infected fruit stopped growing and then stromatization of
16 mycelia and mummification occurred as hard and black areas under the fruit peel. *M.*
17 *linhartiana* was identified from all 60 symptomatic fruit collected from the quince
18 orchards. The fungus, which was identified by its characteristic mycelium, grew from
19 96% of pieces of mummified fruit that were placed on acidified PDA. Most affected
20 fruit fell from the tree to the orchard floor during the spring and early summer. Some
21 fruit, however, remained attached to the shoots for at least 1 year.

22 **Effect of temperature on mycelial growth and apothecial development**

1 Both isolates of *M. linhartiana* grew on PSA at temperatures ranging from 5 to 35°C
2 (Fig. 4). Growth rate (mm per day) was plotted against temperature and the best
3 relationship was described by a third degree polynomial ($Y = aT^3 + bT^2 + cT + d$; Fig.
4 4). The four model parameters (a, b, c, d) were significant ($P < 0.05$) for both isolates.
5 The optimal temperature for mycelial growth was 22.5°C for MON-08 and 22.3°C for
6 MON-09. Optimal temperatures and area under the curve of mycelial growth did not
7 differ between the two isolates (Student's t -test; $P > 0.05$) but the maximum growth rate
8 was greater for MON-08 than for MON-09 (Student's t -test; $P = 0.011$).

9 Apothecia of *M. linhartiana* developed on mummified quince fruit (Fig. 1d) at
10 temperatures ranging from 6 to 24°C (Table 2). Rate of development of apothecia
11 increased linearly with increasing incubation temperature (Table 2). Longevity,
12 however, was greater at low than at high temperatures (*data not shown*).

13 **Apothecial development and ascospore dynamics in orchards**

14 *M. linhartiana* apothecia developed on aborted and mummified fruit that remained on
15 the orchard floor from February to April. These fruit were buried, partly buried or on
16 the soil surface. Fallen quince leaves and weeds usually protected the apothecia from
17 direct sunlight and desiccation. In 2006 and 2007, the first apothecia were observed at
18 the beginning of March, coinciding with quince budbreak. In 2008, the first apothecia
19 were observed on 21 February, again coinciding with budbreak. The number of
20 apothecia per m² ranged from 5.3 to 28.7 and differed between years and orchards.
21 Inoculum potential also differed between years and orchards (Table 3).

22 Because of their characteristic morphology (shape, size and colour), *M.*
23 *linhartiana* ascospores were easily identified on the spore sampler tape. Empty asci or

1 asci with two to eight ascospores were also sometimes present on the tape. Spores were
2 collected from 3 March to 6 April in 2006, and from 5 March to 23 April in 2007, and
3 spore concentration in the air was much greater in 2007 than in 2006 (Fig. 5). In 2006,
4 ascospore concentration was maximum in mid- to late March, which coincided with
5 budbreak, and then decreased gradually until late April, when no spores were detected.

6 **Relationship between inoculum, disease and weather variables**

7 The incidence of monilia disease (the percentage of shoots with symptoms of *M.*
8 *linhartiana* infection) increased linearly with maximum inoculum potential ($P = 0.002$;
9 $R^2 = 0.922$; $R_a^2 = 0.902$; Table 3). The incidence of monilia disease was not correlated
10 (Pearson test; $P > 0.05$) with numbers of mummified fruit/m², numbers of apothecia per
11 mummified fruit or the numbers of apothecia/m² (Table 3).

12 In 2006, daily ascospore concentration in the air was only related to rainfall on
13 the same day of capture (multiple linear regression: $P = 0.007$). But it was not related to
14 rainfall on the days before ascospore capture or to the rest of weather parameters studied
15 (temperature, relative humidity and wind speed) on the same day or on days before
16 ascospore capture. In 2007, ascospore concentration was not related ($P > 0.05$) to any
17 weather parameter (Fig. 5). The cumulative numbers of ascospores collected were
18 described by a logistic model in both years ($P < 0.001$; R^2 and $R_a^2 > 0.90$). The fitted
19 model was $\text{Ln}(Y_i/(1-Y_{max})) = -25.092 + 0.315X_i$ in 2006 and $\text{Ln}(Y_i/(1-Y_{max})) = -10.031$
20 $+ 0.12X_i$ in 2007. The number of ascospores collected on a particular day was
21 positively correlated with inoculum potential on that day (Pearson Test; $r = 0.707$; $P =$
22 0.022) based on data from both years. This correlation improved when the number of
23 ascospores collected on a particular day was replaced by the number of ascospores
24 accumulated during a 72-h period that included the day on which inoculum potential

1 was assessed and one day before and one day after assessment (Pearson test; $r = 0.851$;
2 $P = 0.002$). The linear relationship between the number of spores collected on a
3 particular day and inoculum potential calculated on that day was also indicated by
4 regression ($R^2 = 0.918$; $R_a^2 = 0.906$; $P < 0.001$; Fig. 6). The number of ascospores
5 collected did not have a diurnal pattern (*data not shown*).

6 **Discussion**

7 The importance of the epidemics of monilia disease on quince in southern Spain was
8 confirmed with as many as 91% of the quince shoots in one orchard diseased.
9 Incidences of monilia disease near 90% have also been reported in Italy and Turkey
10 (Viennot-Bourgin, 1941; Altinyay, 1972; Batra, 1991). In other years in the current
11 study, however, the pathogen caused a natural and beneficial fruit thinning and infected
12 fewer than 7% of the shoots, suggesting that the development of monilia epidemics
13 could depend greatly on the quantity of primary inoculum and weather conditions,
14 which were very variable among studied years.

15 Apothecia were found on mummified fruit, which overwintered on the soil
16 surface or buried < 2 cm. Morphological characteristics of the apothecia, ascospores,
17 asci and paraphyses of isolates of *M. linhartiana* from Spain agreed with description of
18 previous studies in France, Italy, Portugal and Turkey (Altinyay, 1972; Tomaz & Costa,
19 1980; Batra, 1991). Like others *Monilinia* species in the *Disjunctoriae* section (Batra,
20 1991), conidia of *Monilia cydoniae*, the anamorph of *M. linhartiana*, were formed on
21 affected leaves and shoots (Fig. 1b), but not on mummified young fruit or culture
22 media. Poor sporulation in culture media of *Monilinia* species in *Disjunctoriae* section
23 could be related to the parasitic specialization of these pathogens (Batra, 1991).

1 *Monilinia linhartiana* was not pathogenic on ripe quince fruit, unlike *M.*
2 *fructigena* and *M. laxa*, but was easily isolated from mummified developing fruit that
3 remained hanging on trees or fell to the orchard floor. On the contrary, younger fruit are
4 less susceptible to infection by *M. fructigena* conidia even when fresh wounds are
5 inoculated (Xu & Robinson, 2000). The affected young fruit of quince were probably
6 infected by conidia via gynoecial pathway by open flowers (Batra, 1991).

7 Genetic information has been published on *Monilinia* species that cause brown
8 rot of pomes and stone fruits (Carbone & Kohn, 1993). In this study, the 5.8S-ITS
9 region of *M. linhartiana* was sequenced for the first time. Phylogenetic analysis based
10 on 5.8S-ITS region sequences showed that *Monilinia* is a polyphyletic taxon formed for
11 three Groups. However, the Groups I and II show relatively low bootstrap values (81
12 and 67%, respectively), the species within each Group have common morphological and
13 biological characteristics (Batra, 1991; Holst-Jensen *et al.*, 1997). Based on the current
14 study, isolates of *M. linhartiana* fall into the *Disjunctoriae* section (group II) of
15 *Monilinia* spp. and they showed greater affinity with *M. amelanchieris* and *M. mali* than
16 with other species infecting rosaceous hosts. These results support those of Holst-Jensen
17 *et al.* (1997) for the isolate (Z73783), which was previously described as *M. johnsonii*
18 but seems to have been misidentified. Small differences in the ITS-5.8S region and the
19 temperature effect were found among the *M. linhartiana* isolates. These differences may
20 be derived from the recombination via sexual reproduction observed in this species.

21 Mycelia of *M. linhartiana* grew at temperatures ranging from 5 to 30°C with an
22 optimum near 22.5°C. Tomaz & Costa (1980) reported that optimal temperature for
23 mycelial growth of this species was 24°C. *M. linhartiana* ascospores can germinate at
24 temperatures ranging from 7 to 30°C (Altinyay, 1972). In general, apothecia of the

1 pathogen developed faster at higher temperatures in the current study but the longevity
2 of apothecia decreased as temperatures increased from 6 to 24°C. Similar results were
3 reported for *M. fructicola* and *M. vaccinii-corymbosi* (Hong & Michailides, 1998;
4 Wharton & Schilder, 2005). This suggests that during the cool weather of late winter
5 and early spring, *M. linhartiana* inoculum might be available for long periods.

6 The number of apothecia of *M. linhartiana* on the soil surface ranged from 5.3 to
7 28.7 apothecia per m², which is greater than the number (4.4 apothecia per m²) of *M.*
8 *fructicola* apothecia that was found in peach orchards in New Zealand (Tate & Wood,
9 2000). This higher number of apothecia for *M. linhartiana* than for *M. fructicola* could
10 result from the fact that *M. linhartiana* requires a sexual stage to complete its life cycle
11 (Fig 7; Cabello, 2008) whereas *M. fructicola* does not. Both *M. fructicola* ascospores
12 and conidia can cause primary infection of blossoms, leading to blossom blight in
13 spring (Michailides *et al.*, 2007).

14 In our study, the number of ascospores collected was related with inoculum
15 potential (Fig. 6) but not with the percentage of shoots infected by *M. linhartiana*. The
16 lack of relationship between ascospore concentration in the air and shoot infection
17 during 2006 and 2007 probably was due to different weather conditions during leaf
18 development (from C1 to D2 phenological stages) in the two years. In 2006, these host
19 development stages coincided with the rainy season and shoot infection was 91%. This
20 heavy infection leaved a large number of mummified fruit as inoculum source for the
21 next year. In 2007, however, shoot infection was only 22%, probably because rain was
22 very limited during this period. After quince leaves have developed, the risk of leaf
23 infection is probably low, as has been shown for blueberry (Milholland, 1974; Ramsdell
24 *et al.*, 1975).

1 The life cycle of *M. linhartiana* in southern Spain was closely related to host
2 phenology (Fig. 7) and was similar to the life cycles of other *Monilinia* spp. in the
3 section *Disjunctoriae* (Lehman & Oudemans, 1997; 2000; Scherm & Savelle, 2003).
4 Such synchrony between pathogen and host is reasonable because *M. linhartiana*
5 ascospores are capable of infection only during the very short periods when young
6 vegetative tissues are present on the host (Batra, 1991; Lehman & Oudemans, 1997;
7 Scherm & Savelle, 2003). For *M. vaccinii-corymbosi* on blueberry, pathogen–host
8 synchrony occurs because development of apothecia and budbreak require a similar
9 cold period (chill hours) (Milholland, 1974; Lehman & Oudemans, 1997). It is possible
10 that the same biological mechanism of synchronization occurs for *M. linhartiana*
11 because apothecial development was induced when mummified fruit were incubated for
12 3 months at 4°C (J. Moral & A. Trapero, *unpublished data*).

13 In this study, *M. linhartiana* ascospores apparently infected quince leaves and
14 produced conidia, which serve as secondary inoculum for flower infection. Foliage
15 infected by *M. linhartiana* emitted an aromatic odour like the quince flowers. Blueberry
16 foliage modified in a similar manner by *M. vaccinii-corymbosi* attracts flower-foraging
17 insects, which act as vectors of conidia (Batra, 1991). This observation was already
18 noted by Schellenberg for quince leaves infected by *M. linhartiana*, suggesting that
19 insects are attracted by the odour and carried the conidia of the fungus to the stigmas of
20 the flowers (Wormald, 1926).

21 The life cycle of monilia disease of quince in southern Spain established in this
22 study (Fig. 7) should be used to define the strategy for disease control. Since primary
23 infection is caused by ascospores from mummified fruit on the soil, coinciding with the
24 presence of young and expanding leaves in the host, control strategy should be oriented

1 to reduce the inoculum source (mummified fruit that overwintered on the soil surface)
2 and to protect young leaves with fungicides. This strategy subsequently limits
3 secondary infection (flower infection) due to conidia because it reduces the source of
4 conidia produced on infected leaves and the epidemic has only one secondary cycle
5 without the ripe fruit rot phase characteristic of some other species of *Monilinia*.

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2 **Table 1** Isolates of *Monilinia* spp. used in this study

Isolate ^a	Species	Host	Origin	Year
MON-01	<i>M. laxa</i>	<i>Prunus armeniaca</i>	Zaragoza ^b	2005
MON-02	<i>M. laxa</i>	<i>Prunus armeniaca</i>	Murcia ^b	2005
MON-03	<i>M. fructigena</i>	<i>Malus domestica</i>	La Coruña ^b	2005
MON-04	<i>M. fructigena</i>	<i>Prunus domestica</i>	La Coruña ^b	2005
MON-05	<i>M. fructigena</i>	<i>Malus domestica</i>	Zaragoza ^b	2005
MON-06	<i>M. linhartiana</i>	<i>Cydonia oblonga</i>	El Palancar ^c	2005
MON-07	<i>M. linhartiana</i>	<i>Cydonia oblonga</i>	El Palancar ^c	2005
MON-08	<i>M. linhartiana</i>	<i>Cydonia oblonga</i>	Zagrilla Baja ^c	2005
MON-09	<i>M. linhartiana</i>	<i>Cydonia oblonga</i>	El Palancar ^c	2005
MON-10	<i>M. linhartiana</i>	<i>Cydonia oblonga</i>	El Palancar ^c	2006
MON-11	<i>M. linhartiana</i>	<i>Cydonia oblonga</i>	El Palancar ^c	2006
MON-12	<i>M. linhartiana</i>	<i>Cydonia oblonga</i>	Zagrilla Baja ^c	2006
MON-13	<i>M. linhartiana</i>	<i>Cydonia oblonga</i>	Zagrilla Baja ^c	2006
MON-14	<i>M. linhartiana</i>	<i>Cydonia oblonga</i>	El Palancar ^c	2006
MON-15	<i>M. linhartiana</i>	<i>Cydonia oblonga</i>	El Palancar ^c	2006
MON-16	<i>M. linhartiana</i>	<i>Cydonia oblonga</i>	El Palancar ^c	2006
MON-17	<i>M. linhartiana</i>	<i>Cydonia oblonga</i>	El Palancar ^c	2006

33 ^aIsolates of *M. laxa* and *M. fructigena* were provided by Dr. A. de Cal from diseased fruit and
 34 isolates of *M. linhartiana* were collected by authors of this study from diseased leaves.

35 ^bProvinces of Spain.

36 ^cQuince orchards in Córdoba Province.

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Table 2 Effect of temperature on development of apothecia of *Monilinia linhartiana* on quince fruit^a

Temperature (°C)	R^{2b}	R_a^{2b}	P value ^b	Slope (= a) ^b
6	0.90	0.89	< 0.001	0.092 c ^c
12	0.96	0.95	< 0.001	0.131 b
18	0.90	0.89	< 0.001	0.167 b
24	0.98	0.93	< 0.001	0.263 a

^aMummified quince fruit with apothecial initials were incubated at four constant temperatures in moisture chambers and the phenological stage of apothecia [from 1 (apothecium cup not formed) to 5 (senescing apothecium with few or no ascospores) (Cabello, 2008)] was assessed periodically.

^bParameters of regressions for apothecial development against time [Phenological stage of apothecia (0-5) = $a \times t$ (t = time in days)].

^cMeans (n = 24) followed by the same letter are not significantly different according to least significant difference test at $P = 0.05$.

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Table 3 Inoculum variables and incidence of quince shoots with symptoms of *Monilinia linhartiana* infection in different years and different orchards

Orchard	Year	Mummified fruit/m ²	Apothecia/mummified fruit	Apothecia/m ²	MIP ^{ab}	Incidence ^b (%)
Zagrilla Baja	2006	4.7	3.1	14.6	35.3	60.2
El Palancar	2006	6.7	2.7	18.0	47.0	91.5
Zagrilla Baja	2007	9.6	3.0	28.7	27.7	21.9
El Palancar	2007	6.3	3.1	19.2	21.5	20.5
El Palancar	2008	2.2	2.4	5.3	10.8	10.5

^aMaximum inoculum potential (MIP) was the maximum annual value of inoculum potential (IP) calculated as $IP = (\sum n_i \times e_i) / S$, where n_i = number of apothecia, e_i = phenological stage (< 5) of each apothecium and S = sampled area (4 m²).

^bDisease incidence was correlated with MIP: Incidence (%) = $1.58 \times MIP$ [$P = 0.002$; $R^2 = 0.922$; $R_a^2 = 0.902$ (Campbell & Madden, 1990)].

Figure 1 Symptoms of monilia disease of quince caused by *Monilinia linhartiana*: **(a)** shoot blight, **(b)** leaf blotch with abundant production of *M. linhartiana* conidia mainly along the leaf veins **(c)** infected young fruit (arrow) together with a healthy fruit, **(d)** apothecia produced from mummified fruit.

Figure 2 Incidence (%) of quince shoots with symptoms of *Monilinia linhartiana* infection in different orchards and years. Bars represent the average of 10 trees. Vertical lines represent the standard errors of the means. Orchards: La Mendaña (▣); El Algar (▤); Zagrilla Baja (▥); and El Palancar (▦)

Figure 3 Maximum likelihood phylogram inferred with PHYML from the 5.8S-ITS sequences of *Monilinia* spp., *Monilia mumecola*, *Ovulinia azaleae*, *Sclerotinia sclerotiorum*, under a GTR+G nucleotide substitution model considering *Monilinia megalospora* as root. Branch lengths are scaled in terms of the expected number of substitutions per site. Numbers above branches represent ML bootstrap values (only values greater than 50% are shown).

Figure 4 Effect of temperature on mycelial growth of *Monilinia linhartiana* on potato sucrose agar. Each value is the mean of three replications. Isolates: MON-08 (◆) and MON-09 (□)

Figure 5 Numbers of *Monilinia linhartiana* ascospores (—) collected per m³ per day, mean relative humidity (RH, %; - - -), mean temperature (°C; ·····), and rainfall (mm/day; ■) in a quince orchard in southern Spain. Ascospore density in the air was measured with a Burkard volumetric spore trap located 1 m above soil surface in 2006 (a) and 2007 (b). Phenological stages of quince from B (bud swelling) to H (fruit setting) are according to Martínez-Valero *et al.* (2001).

Figure 6 Linear relationship ($Y = 6.538 X$; $R^2 = 0.918$; $R_a^2 = 0.906$; $P < 0.0001$) between the density of *Monilinia linhartiana* ascospores in air (spores/m³ air day) and *M. linhartiana* inoculum potential in a quince orchard (El Palancar) in 2006 and 2007. Inoculum potential (IP) was calculated as $IP = (\sum n_i \times e_i) / S$, where n_i = number of apothecia, e_i = phenological stage (1-4) of each apothecium, and S = sampled area (20 m²).

Figure 7 Life cycle of monilia disease of quince tree caused by *Monilia linhartiana* in Southern Spain.